

Murabaha on Islamic Financial Inclusion: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract

This study aims to determine the mapping of research topics around the Murabahah contracts in the Islamic Financial Inclusion using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometrics study and library research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications regarding the Murabahah contract; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometrics visualization regarding the Murabahah contracts based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the Murabahah contract using a library research study. The results of the study show that: (1) based on the mapping of the distribution of journals publications, there are 1754 journal publications regarding the Murabahah contract; (2) based on VOSviewer's bibliometric study mapping, the network visualization results around the Murabaha contracts are divided into 9 clusters and 102 topics items; (3) based on the mapping of library research studies, there are 8 main topics surrounding the Murabaha contracts. The differences between this research and previous research is that this study explains and maps all research topics around the Murabahah contract so that future researchers can find the research gaps around the Murabahah contract. The implication and contribution of this research are that there is a mapping of research topics around the Murabahah contract, which is often or rarely researched by researchers to be a references for future researchers.

Keywords: Murabaha; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Inclusion

Introduction

An agreement between two parties or what is called a contract of ownership important meaning in aspects of human life and is the basis of many many daily activities. The contract also takes the form of a series of transactions against sharia economics, by using this contract activities in the form of business and enterprise able to run smoothly. The Murabahah contract is the contract used for transactions sell buy goods with explain price Which obtained as well as profit Which has agreed upon by the buyer and seller of the goods. Murabahah is a sale and purchase agreement goods with price sell a number Which obtained And added Also profit Which has been promised and the seller must explain the costs obtained above goods Which has purchased. Summary the is transaction from contract Murabaha, this contract does not have to be in the form of installment payments but can also be in cash after accept the item. Contract Murabaha is product financing Which superior by Syariah banking. Murabahah is often referred to as a sale and purchase agreement, where the seller and the buyer makes an agreement, so that the Islamic financial institution records it on agreement contract the. Implementation contract murabahah on institution finance sharia classified as financing consumptive And financing productive. Financing consumptive is financing Which relate with activity consumption a customer, like purchase vehicle motorcycle, credit home

ownership. Meanwhile, productive financing is related to investment and capital business.

Study scientific around contract Murabaha very Lots Which study from period time to time based on search from site study scientific Garuda (Guard Reference Digital) on period 2022 found 1490 study study about contract murabahah. This shows that Murabahah contracts are in great demand among the public. Objective study This is For map topics study around contract Murabaha on Industry Finance Sharia in Indonesia with use: (1) studies bibliometrics VOSviewer To use analyze And learn map development literature in publication something field science with make map network metadata; And (2) studies library research To use analyze, identify And me- review articles from journal national accredited Sinta. Difference study This with research previously is on study This explain and map all over topic study around contract Murabaha, so that researcher furthermore can know emptiness study around contract Murabaha. Implications And contribution study This is exists mapping topics study around contract Murabaha Which often or seldom researched by researcher, so that can become reference for researcher furthermore.

Literature Review

Contract Bai' Al-Murabahah is contract sell buy goods with set mark product to buyer, buyer do payment with price Which has been set. This murabahah agreement takes into consideration that DSN-MUI has determined fatwa related murabaha, Good For banking, company, financing, service finance capable activity business other, However Not yet set fatwa about contract sell buy murabahah For scope Which more wide as fatwa parent (DSN-MUI, 2017).

Bibliometrics is a mathematical method For know publication around studies scientific on library. Bibliometrics is method study descriptive For know pattern author, amount collaboration, level production, something article (Dubyna et al., 2022). VOSViewer This is program from computer Which can developed For compile And see map bibliometrics. Offer function text-mining so that it can be used to compile and visualize a network or connection (correlation) in A quotation shaped article nor publishing. Map publication is displayed with function And various method, like scrolling, mapping zoom and searching system so you can map a map article as well as publications more detail (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Library research is scientific literacy which aims to find out something topic. Library research describe enhancement something topic certain. Library research a study can do development And identification related theory with accurate in research results. Just like we do data collection or information, evaluate research results, theory and data, and analyze the results publications such as books and articles can also be referred to as statements that have been made arranged by previous research (El-Halaby et al., 2021).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, that is method quantitative on studies bibliometrics And method qualitative on studies library researchs. Object his research is contract Murabaha. Type data Which used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is research journal articles regarding the Murabahah agreement on Financial Industry Sharia.

Source taking data originate from search journal national accredited Sinta through website Garuda (Garba Reference Digital) And software Perish/Harzing. Tool analysis data use software Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, And

VOSviewer. Data collection techniques include: (1) opening the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category saying the key “Murabahah” in the whole year period; (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, And identify title journal Which double; (3) download files format RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) from all over journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into software Mendeley Desktop.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around contract Hawalah use Microsoft Excel And Mendeley Desktop based on year publishing; (2) map results visualization network bibliometrics And trend publication journal around contract Hawalah use software algorithm VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) based on amount cluster And the item; And (3) map topic study around contract Hawalah use studies library research (Budianto, 2023).

Results and Discussion

Mapping Spread Publication Scientific About Contract Murabaha on Industry Finance Sharia

There is 1754 journal national accredited Sinta based on results data collection using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop from website Garuda (Garba Reference Digital) And software Perish/Harzing during period 2003 to year 2022. The result is as following:

Table 1. Data publication scientific around Murabahah Agreement based on year

Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication	Year	Amount Publication
2004	1	2012	29	2018	152

mudharabah, musyarakah, financing musyarakah, influence financing, banking sharia, studies case, year.

- Cluster 3 consists from 16 topic, that is: analysis, application psak, bank sharia, psak, bmt, dsn mui iv, kpr, sharia banking, murabahah financing, application, study case on bpr, sharia, murabahah.
- Cluster 4 consists of 15 topics, namely: analysis of the influence of third party funds, capital adequacy ratio, car, deposit ratio, equity, fdr, financing, indonesia period, kspp, influence capital adequacy ratio, return, certificate wadiah bank Indonesia, financing murabahah.
- Cluster 5 consists from 12 topic, that is: assets, customers, effect, influence, murabaha, murabahah financing, non-performing financing, profitability, ROA, Sharia bank, sharia commercial bank, banking sharia.
- Cluster 6 consists from 11 topic, that is: analysis factors, bank financing people sharia, bank general sharia, bpr, ijarah, Indonesia year, istishna, npf, influence financing murabaha, studies case, variable moderation.
- Cluster 7 consists from 6 topic, that is: cases study, implementation, murabaha contracts, murabahah agreement, psak, sharia banking.
- Cluster 8 consists from 4 topic, that is: bank people Indonesia sharia, PT, company, tbk.
- Cluster 9 consists from 2 topic, that is: murabaha, application psak.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Application Contract Murabaha

In this sub-chapter, the research subject concerns the implementation of the Murabahah contract in Institution Finance Sharia, divided become 2 (two) parts (Budianto, 2023), that is:

First, there are 7 research topics related to the implementation of contracts Murabahah on Sharia Financial Inclusion in general, namely: (1) Its application in Bank General Sharia; (2) Implementation in Bank Financing People Sharia (BPRS); (3) Implementation in Cooperative Sharia; (4) Implementation in public; (5) Application in Non-Bank Institutions; (6) Application to precious metal investments; And (7) Application to platforms peers to peers lending.

Second, there is 16 topic study Which related with application Murabahah contract financing on Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Implementation at Sharia Commercial Banks; (2) Implementation in Community Institutions/Mosques; (3) Implementation at Baitul Maal Wat Tamwil (BMT); (4) Application to financing take over; (5) Application to education financing; (6) Application to home ownership/mortgage financing; (7) Application to vehicle financing motorized; (8) Application to business capital; (9) Application to Micro Enterprises, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs); (10) Application to other consumer products; (11) Implementation on product productive other; (12) Implementation on sector real/agricultural; (13) Application to retirees; (14) Application to products Financing Well-being Employee (PKP); (15) Implementation on Program National Community Empowerment (SPP PNPM-MP); and (16) Its application to product Credit financing People's Business (KUR) Sharia.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Influence Contract Murabaha

In this sub-chapter, the subject of research concerns the influence of the Murabahah contract on Sharia Financial Inclusion, divided into 2 (two) parts (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Goddess, 2023) (Rohimah et al., 2023),

that is:

First, there are 2 research topics related to the influence of contracts Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia in a way general, that is: (1) Its influence to yield; And (2) The influence to the total asset.

Second, there is 28 topic study Which related with influence financing Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) The influence to profitability; (2) The influence to Return On Equity (ROE); (3) The influence to Return On Assets (ROA); (4) The influence to Financing to Deposit Ratio (FDR); (5) The effect on Non-Performing Financing (NPF); (6) The influence to MSMEs; (7) The influence to alleviation poverty; (8) The effect on agency; (9) The effect on increasing income business; (10) The influence to profit clean; (11) The influence to well-being customers; (12) The influence to liquidity; (13) The influence to volume financing Mudharabah; (14) The influence to profitability; (15) The influence to Remainder Results Business (SHU); (16) The influence to mark company; (17) The influence to performance company; (18) The influence to performance finance; (19) The influence to operating revenues; (20) Its influence on the company's health level; (21) The influence to giving profit; (22) The influence to income distribution of funds; (23) Its influence on farming production; (24) Its influence to development business; (25) The influence to loan sharks; (26) The influence to sales turnover; and (27) The impact on SME customers' profits; And (28) Its influence on margins Murabaha.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Study Juridical around Contract Murabaha

In this sub-chapter, the research subject revolves around the perspective of Islamic law, law positive And legislation around contract Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia, is divided into 2 (two) parts (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023), that is:

First, there are 20 research topics related to legal perspectives Islam, positive law and legislation surrounding Murabahah contracts on Inclusion Sharia Finance, namely: (1) SOP for Murabahah contracts according to the Koran and Hadith; (2) Teachings Ethics Islam in Marketing Product Contract Murabaha; (3) Guidelines Accountancy Indonesian Sharia Banking (PAPSI) 2013; (4) Implementation according to the DSN-fatwa MUI; (5) Application according to Islamic law; (6) Implementation of the DSN-MUI fatwa in product installments gold; (7) Completion Dispute in Body Arbitrage Sharia National MUI; (8) The style of the DSN-MUI fatwa school of thought in the Murabahah agreement; (9) Murabahah critical point in the DSN-MUI fatwa; (10) Sharia principles in Murabahah transaction contracts; (11) Rights option in sell buy Murabaha according to fatwa DSN-MUI; (12) Evaluation practice Murabahah according to fiqh law; (13) The validity of the Murabahah contract deed is based on sharia compliance; (14) Murabahah Agreement according to Abdullah Saeed; (15) Murabaha in the perspective of four schools of thought; (16) Murabahah between validity and doubt law; (17) Application of Murabahah principles in Islamic agreements; (18) Implementation Murabahah fines according to the DSN-MUI fatwa; (19) Judicial review of agreements credit ownership House; And (20) Problems fatwa deep scholars contract Murabaha.

Second, there are 25 research topics related to legal perspectives Islam, positive law and legislation surrounding Murabahah financing in Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) Accountancy contract Murabaha according to PSAK Sharia No. 50, 55, 59, 60, 102, 105, 111; (2) Implementation according to the DSN-MUI fatwa; (3) Implementation according to KHES; (4) Application according to the VAT Law; (5) Application according to fiqh/syariah law; (6) Application according to Positive Law; (7) Regulations Bank Indonesia No. 10

Year 2008 about Restructurisation Financing Murabaha; (8) Legal certainty of ownership of the object of the agreement in the Murabahah financing deed; (9) Completion dispute financing Murabaha in Court Religion; (10) Completion dispute Financing Murabaha Troubled According to Fatwa DSN-MUI; (11) Completion dispute Financing Murabaha according to Law Economy Sharia; (12) Completion default in Court Religion; (13) Performance financing Murabaha post enactment Constitution deletion tax multiple; (14) Completion action Side Streaming in Perspective Fiqh Muamalah; (15) Handling Financing Murabaha Troubled; (16) Law margin/price murabahah according to the perspective of Islamic law; (17) Authority of the Settlement Body Dispute Consumer in solution dispute Financing Murabaha; (18) Position law contract Insurance in contract financing Murabaha; (19) Murabahah Financing in the Hadith Book of Al-Tis'ah; (20) Murabahah Law And Wow in One transaction according to fatwa DSN-MUI; (21) Confession annuity-based Murabahah profits according to the maqashid sharia perspective; (22) Fine scheduling repeat financing Murabaha according to law Islam; (23) Overview fiqh economy to financing capital Work; (24) Synchronization regulations financing Murabaha; And (25) Synchronization arrangement status ownership goods on financing Deep murabahah law banking sharia.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Effort Development Contract Murabaha

In sub-chapter This, subject study around effort development contract Murabahah on Sharia Financial Inclusion, is divided into 2 (two) parts (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Goddess, 2023), that is:

First, there is 7 topic study Which related with effort development contract Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia in a way general, that is:

(1) Murakkabah Agreement; (2) Murabahah direct; (3) Standardization of Murabahah contracts as Financial Intermediaries; (4) Multiple contracts between Murabahah and Rahn; (5) Application on sharia investment to maintain business stability; (6) Implementation of the Murabahah contract on contract Muzara'ah; And (7) Application UTAUT to innovation instalment book make a promise Murabaha.

Second, there is 19 topic study Which related with effort development financing Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia, that is: (1) Contract Murabahah bil Wakalah financing; (2) Standard Contract; (3) Application 5C (Character, Capacity, Capital, Conditional, Collateral); (4) Murabahah Financing Fintech Based; (5) Solutions to suppress the Non-Performing Financing (NPF) level; (6) Manipulation development And enhancement quality product financing Murabaha; (7) Application pay post-harvest on return financing Murabaha; (8) Implementation of Musyarakah Mutanaqisah as an alternative to Murabahah financing; (9) Method base data fuzzy tahini with weighting entropy in taking decision appropriateness financing Murabaha; (10) Restructurisation financing Murabaha problematic; (11) Strategy marketing contract Murabaha (personal selling); (12) Quality Source Power Man to Financing Murabaha; (13) Accompaniment program application financing Murabaha for student; (14) Optimization Murabahah financing at sharia financial institutions; (15) Internal preventive efforts maintain credibility and public trust; (16) Efforts to prevent cancellation financing agreement by the prospective debtor due to incompatibility of the sale and purchase object; (17) Update financing Murabaha; (18) Reformulation price on financing Murabaha; and (19) Murabahah-based information system for financing services website.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which

Influence Financing Murabaha

In this sub-chapter, the subject of research revolves around influencing factors financing Murabaha on Inclusion Finance Sharia shared become 6 (six) part, that is:

First, there is 36 factor Which influence financing Murabaha, that is:

(1) Operational Expenses to Operating Income (BOPO); (2) BI Rate; (3) BI 7 Day (Reverse) repo rate; (4) Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR); (5) Credit Scoring; (6) Currency Exchange /exchange rate; (7) Current Ratio; (8) Third Party Funds (DPK); (9) Debt to Equity Ratio (DER); (10) Financing to Deposits Ratio (FDR); (11) Price gold; (12) Inflation; (13) Amount Money circulating (M1); (14) Causality Factor Internal; (15) Margins profit; (16) Capital; (17) Net Operating Margins (NOM); (18) Non Performing Financing (NPF); (19) Product Domestic Gross (GDP); (20) Quick Ratio; (21) Return On Assets (ROA); (22) Certificate Bank Indonesia Sharia (SBIS); (23) Level interest rate Bank Conventional; (24) Bank Indonesia interest rates; (25) Cash; (26) Amount of wadiah savings; (27) Unrestricted investment funds; (28) Capital adequacy ratio; (29) Own capital; (30) Wadiah savings; (31) Mudharabah Deposits; (32) Financial Ratios; (33) Certificate Wadian Bank Indonesia (SWBI); (34) Macro economy; (35) Financing to Assets Ratio; And (36) Rate of Return to Financing Ratio.

Second, there is 32 factor Which influence decision/satisfaction customers choose Murabahah financing, namely: (1) Fixed monthly installments; (2) Flexible can be used for anything; (3) The system is easy; (4) Sales marketing directly to customers; (5) Quality service; (6) Facility; (7) Location; (8) Quality Product; (9) Promotion; (10) Needs; (11) References; (12) Easy procedures; (13) Confidence; (14) Support family And relatives; (15) There is margins And present; (16) Culture; (17) Social; (18) Personal; (19) Psychological; (20) Perception; (21) Interest individual; (22) Guarantee; (23) Knowledge; (24) Price; (25) Characteristics; (26) Margins; (27) Income; (28) Religiosity; (29) Not harmed; (30) Trust; (31) Risk; and (32) Marketing sharia.

Third, there are 3 factors that influence the demand for Murabahah financing, namely: (1) Profit margin level; (2) Gross Domestic Product (GDP); and (3) Inflation. Fourth, there is 20 factor Which influence giving financing Murabaha, that is: (1) Level profit business; (2) Report finance; (3) Usage financing; (4) Ownership guarantee; (5) No own loan other; (6) Dependents life; (7) Connection personal; (8) Capital; (9) Risk failure; (10) Ability repayment; (11) Business constraints; (12) Condition economy; (13) Distance; (14) Condition product; (15) Place/Location of business; (16) Gender; (17) Education level; (18) Long business; (19) Installment amount; And (20) Character.

Fifth, there is 2 factor Which influence enhancement distribution fund through financing Murabaha, namely: (1) Cost Promotion; And (2) Level margins.

Sixth, there are 3 factors that influence the risk of Murabahah financing, that is: (1) Financing to Deposits Ratio (FDR); (2) Burden Operational to Income Operational (BOPO); and (3) System manage.

Seventh, there is 10 factor Which influence smoothness return Murabahah financing, namely: (1) Loan value; (2) Business Experience; (3) Turnover Business; (4) Level Education; (5) Age; (6) Dependents Family; (7) Mark guarantee; (8) Factor economy; (9) Capital social; And (10) Religiosity.

Eighth, there are 2 factors that influence the risk of Murabahah financing, namely: (1) Internal factors include intelligence, interests, talents, motivation and age; (2) Factor external covers environment, education, experience And training.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Factors Which Influence Margins Financing Murabaha

In this sub-chapter, the subject of research revolves around influencing factors Murabahah financing margin in Sharia Financial Inclusion is divided into 3 (three) part, that is:

First, there is 9 factor Which influence margins contract financing Murabahah, namely: (1) Cost of Loanable Fund; (2) Overhead Costs; (3) Risk; (4) Divide Results; (5) Third Party Funds/DPK; (6) Profit/profit targets; (7) Operational Costs on Operational Income/BOPO; (8) Non-Performing Financing; and (9) Cash Ratio.

Second, there is 4 factor Which influence income margins contract Murabahah, namely: (1) Cash Ratio; (2) Murabahah Financing; (3) Financial Ratios profitability; And (4) Ethnic group BI interest.

Third, there is 26 factor in influence determination margins contract Murabaha, that is: (1) Financing Murabaha; (2) Burden Operational to Operating Income (BOPO); (3) Operational Costs; (4) Profit Target (Level desired profit); (5) Cost of Funds; (6) Credit Risk; (7) Average level margin market; (8) Composition funding; (9) Type customers; (10) Condition economy; (11) Cost Overheads; (12) Volume Financing; (13) For results; (14) Process financing; (15) Amount nominal/ceiling; (16) Period time; (17) Percentage margins; (18) Method details installments; (19) For Results Fund Party Third (DPK); (20) BI Rate; (21) Financing to Deposits Ratio (FDR); (22) Inflation; (23) Level credit interest rates; (24) Board Supervisor Sharia; (25) Deposit bank conventional; And (26) Mark justice.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Murabahah Contract Guarantees/Collateral

In this sub-chapter, there are 9 research subjects regarding contract guarantees/collateral Murabahah on Sharia Financial Inclusion, namely: (1) Partner's responsibility towards destroyed fiduciary collateral; (2) Encumbrances guarantee right dependents; (3) Auction of Murabahah collateral objects; (4) Application of fiduciary guarantees for financing Murabaha; (5) Provision premium insurance as guarantee to financing Murabaha; (6) Power to sell collateral for Murabahah bil Wakalah contract financing in Religious courts; (7) Fiduciary Guarantee as a legal protection measure for creditor according to decision court great; (8) Execution object guarantee fiduciary; And (9) Strategy solution execution to object guarantee in financing Murabaha.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around Issue Other Which Related with Contract Murabaha

In sub-chapter This, subject study around issues Which related with contract Murabahah on Sharia Financial Inclusion is divided into 2 (two) parts (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023), that is:

First, there are 35 issues related to the Murabahah contract, namely: (1) Change Contract Murabaha caused exists Contract Wow in inside; (2) Challenge application Contract Murabaha; (3) Problem application Contract Murabaha; (4) Differences in transactions between the implementation of the Murabahah contract in the past and present time; (5) Differences in Murabahah contract transactions between theory and practice; (6) Reasons why women choose Murabahah contracts; (7) Reasons why non-Muslims choose the contract Murabaha; (8) Tax Increase Mark on Contract Murabaha; (9) Difference use method confession income margins murabahah to quality profit; (10) The role of women as financing policy makers and customers; (11) Sharia Compliance practice murabaha; (12) Meaning Murabaha according to Hermeneutics of Intentionalism; (13) Implementation of profit rate negotiations on contract Murabaha; (14) Billing Murabaha in accordance Standard

Operational Procedure (SOUP); (15) The concept of justice for nabasah in the Murabahah contract; (16) Concept of force majeure in Murabahah contracts; (17) The concept of welfare for nabasah in the contract Murabaha; (18) Account officer competency and information asymmetry on performance Murabaha; (19) Clause overmacht in contract Murabaha; (20) Diversity meaning of Murabahah; (21) Application of the principle of good faith in the Murabahah contract; (22) Role Notary Public in contract Murabaha; (23) Right khiyar on contract Murabaha; (24) Critics regarding the implementation of the Murabahah agreement; (25) The concept of Murabahah in philosophical dictum Islamic economics; (26) Annuity and proportional methods in Murabahah contracts; (27) Change financing contract Murabaha post conversion from bank conventional become bank sharia; (28) Characteristics norm contract Murabaha; (29) Application auditing based risk on receivables Murabaha; (30) Completion dispute with non approach litigation; (31) Compulsion in Murabahah agreement disputes; (32) Its influence on contract other (Musyarakah Mutanaqisah, Ijarah Muntahiyah Bittamlik); (33) Time Value of Money on contract Murabaha; (34) Protection law party Which make a promise; And (35) Agreement Murabaha between theory And practice.

Second, there is 69 issues Which related with financing contract Murabaha, that is: (1) Influence level risk financing Murabaha to level profitability; (2) Influence level margins Murabaha to Financing to Deposits Ratio (FDR); (3) The influence of Murabahah margin levels on Non-Performing Financing (NPF); (4) Influence level margins Murabaha to enhancement capital; (5) Influence income margins financing Murabaha to profitability; (6) Influence income margins financing Murabaha to profit clean; (7) Influence income margins financing Murabaha to for results savings; (8) Influence income margins financing Murabaha to bonus wadiah; (9) Change make a loss for customers defaulting on Murabahah financing; (10) Effect of margin on growth rate of sharia mortgage partnership financing; (11) Settlement of defaults in Murabahah financing; (12) Settlement of disputes regarding collateral attachment financing Murabaha; (13) The comparison with contract Musharakah in mortgage financing; (14) Comparison with the Ijarah Muntahiya Bit Tamlik agreement in financing mortgage; (15) Management risk financing Murabaha; (16) The dynamic relationship between mudharabah, musyarakah, murabahah financing risks, profitability; (17) Calculation margins Financing Murabaha; (18) Performance Murabahah Financing management; (19) Differences between Murabahah financing Bank; (20) Difference mortgage Conventional Between Bank; (21) Aspect collateral; (22) Abuse contract Wakalah; (23) Control Internal financing Murabaha; (24) Calculation determination margins financing Murabaha; (25) Calculation determination price sell financing Murabaha; (26) Calculation income Murabaha; (27) Application ta'zir on financing Murabaha; (28) Application fine delay/ ta'zir payment installments; (29) Acceleration repayment on Contract Murabaha; (30) Money advance in financing ownership House; (31) System financial management of sharia financing; (32) Partners' rights in financing Murabaha; (33) Application sharia compliance product Murabaha; (34) Principle equality in Murabahah financing; (35) The legal principle of pacta sunt servanda in the Murabahah agreement; (36) Obstacles in the Murabahah financing process; (37) Constraints in implementing Murabahah financing; (38) Validity of risk transfer clause to customers in Murabahah financing agreements; (39) Internal buying power financing Murabaha; (40) Application draft Maslahah on financing Murabaha; (41) Implications determination margins profit on financing Murabaha; (42) Implications change policy pattern repayment financing Murabaha; (43) Indication moral danger on financing Murabaha; (44) Risk reputation on Murabahah margins; (45)

Murabahah and Musawamah Financing; (46) Piece installments financing Murabaha; (47) Supervision financing Murabaha To use minimize financing problematic; (48) Financing Murabaha lil Amir Bis Syira'; (49) Measurement of company profits through Murabahah margin; (50) Completion credit congested on financing Murabaha; (51) Completion financing problematic on financing Murabaha; (52) Impact financing problems with Murabahah financing; (53) Application of the precautionary principle in Murabahah financing; (54) Effect of margin cuts/ Muqashsha Al-Ribhi in receivables Murabaha; (55) Influence frequency melting financing Murabaha to amount customers new; (56) Confession debts in agreement financing Murabaha; (57) Scheduling repeat (rescheduling) bill Murabaha; (58) Murabahah financing management; (59) Management of tabarru' insurance funds sharia in financing Murabaha; (60) Influence comparison composition financing for results, Murabaha And Ijarah to performance company finance; (61) Urgency inclusion contract wow in financing Murabaha; (62) Principle Rida to the Murabahah financing agreement; (63) Application procedures and requirements Murabahah financing; (64) Problems with the ownership status of the object of the financing contract Murabaha; (65) Problematic law sale return assets Which Not yet paid off the payment; (66) Customer perceptions of Murabahah financing practices; (67) Protection buyer to clause standard; (68) Protection law to customers financing Murabaha; And (69) Development MSMEs before And after get Murabahah financing.

Conclusion

Based on results discussion on, can concluded as following: first, based on mapping amount spread publication journal around contract Murabahah in the Islamic Financial Inclusion during the period 2004 to In 2022, from the accredited national journal Sinta, there were 1754 articles publication journal. Second, based on research topic mapping using studies bibliometrics VOSviewer, results visualization network around contract Murabaha on Industry Sharia Finance is divided into 9 clusters and 102 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 19 topic, cluster 2 consists from 17 topic, cluster 3 consists from 16 topic, cluster 4 consists from 15 topics, cluster 5 consists of 12 topics, cluster 6 consists of 11 topics, cluster 7 consists of 6 topics, cluster 8 consists of 4 topics, and cluster 9 consists of 2 topics. Third, based on mapping research topics using a library research study, there are 8 topics related with contract Murabaha on Industry Finance Sharia, that is: (1) Implementation of the Murabahah Agreement; (2) Influence of the Murabahah Agreement; (3) Juridical Study of the Contract Murabaha; (4) Effort Development Contract Murabaha; (5) Factors Which Affecting Murabahah Financing; (6) Factors Affecting Margin Murabaha Financing; (7) Murabahah Agreement Guarantee/Collateral; and (8) Other Issues Which Related with Contract Murabaha on Financial institutions Sharia.

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